

Preliminary Neutron Noise Measurement Using ^{252}Cf for Neutron Decay Constant in a Non-Multiplying System

Ryonosuke Ohashi^{1,*}, Ryoga Hirota¹, Akio Yamamoto¹, Tomohiro Endo¹

¹Nagoya University, Nagoya, Aichi, Japan.

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ABSTRACT

In order to reduce nuclear data-induced bias and uncertainty for the advanced reactor design, this study proposes a simple and low-cost method to measure the neutron decay constant α for a non-multiplying system. The α value is typically measured using the pulsed neutron source method. Instead of using the pulsed neutron source, the neutron noise experiment using a ^{252}Cf spontaneous fission source has the potential to measure the α value even for a simple system made of a non-fissile material only. Based on the heuristic method, the neutron pair detection probability is theoretically derived to clarify that the α value can be analyzed by the Feynman- α method for a three-dimensional homogeneous non-multiplying system. As a preliminary experiment, this study presents the results (i.e., the second-order neutron correlation factor Y and the fitting result of α) of the neutron noise measurement using an approved device of ^{252}Cf with a certification label for a simple system of polyethylene blocks.

Keywords: Neutron Decay Constant, Neutron Noise, Non-Multiplication System, Feynman- α method

1. INTRODUCTION

We have been investigating a surrogate integral experiment for the data assimilation using the neutron decay constant α [1-3] measured for a non-multiplying system. As a preliminary study, we will conduct a neutron noise experiment using an approved device of a ^{252}Cf source with the certification label for a simple system configured with polyethylene blocks.

In order to design advanced reactors, it is necessary to reduce the nuclear data-induced bias and uncertainty. For this purpose, data assimilation using integral experiments is a promising method. For example, the data assimilation using the effective neutron multiplication factor k_{eff} for critical experiments achieves successful outcomes in reactor physics [4,5]. Note, however, that fissile nuclides have larger sensitivity coefficients of k_{eff} with respect to the average number of fission neutrons $\bar{\nu}$ and the fission spectrum χ , and so on [2]. Consequently, the nuclear data of the fissile nuclides tend to be primarily corrected after the data assimilation using k_{eff} , even if there are biases in the nuclear data of non-fissile nuclides. Additionally, it is not easy to carry out new critical experiments for advanced reactors because constructing the new nuclear facilities is becoming increasingly challenging.

* r-ohashi@fermi.energy.nagoya-u.ac.jp

To address the issue with conventional data assimilation using k_{eff} , we focus on another integral experiment of the neutron decay constant α (also known as the inverse of the neutron die-away time). Thanks to the data assimilation using the measured value of α for a simple geometry configured with the target non-fissile nuclides, we expect to selectively improve the bias and the uncertainty due to the target nuclides [3].

Typically, the neutron decay constant α value can be measured by the pulsed neutron method [6–8] even for a non-multiplying system. Note, however, that the conventional α measurement technique requires a charged particle accelerator facility to generate pulsed neutron sources, resulting in high experimental costs and limited machine time.

Therefore, the purpose of this study is to propose an alternative measurement technique that is simpler and easier to perform than using the pulsed neutron source. Specifically, in order to obtain α , we use an approved device of ^{252}Cf with a certification label to measure the neutron noise driven by the multiple emission sources. The remaining sections are organized as follows. Section 2 explains the experimental theory to measure α based on the Feynman- α method [9] for the neutron noise in a steady-state non-multiplying system with the ^{252}Cf spontaneous fission source. Section 3 presents the preliminary neutron noise experiment for a simple non-fissile system configured with polyethylene blocks. Concluding remarks and future research topics are summarized in Section 4.

2. EXPERIMENTAL THEORY

In this section, we explain that the neutron decay constant α can be obtained by analyzing the neutron noise measured in a non-multiplying system with a ^{252}Cf source using the Feynman- α method [9]. To simplify the explanation, the theoretical derivation in this study is based on a heuristic method [10,11] using the one-energy-group neutron diffusion approximation for a one-dimensional slab geometry.

2.1. Green's Function

Let us suppose that one neutron is introduced into a target system as a Dirac's delta function at the spatial position $x = x_0$ and the time $t = t_0$. Then, the expected value of the neutron density $n(x, t|x_0, t_0)$ (also known as the Green's function) satisfies the following equations:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} n(x, t|x_0, t_0) = -\mathbf{A}n(x, t|x_0, t_0) + \delta(x - x_0)\delta(t - t_0), \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{A} is the neutron annihilation operator and is defined as follows under the diffusion approximation in one-dimensional slab geometry:

$$\mathbf{A} \equiv v \left(-D \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + \Sigma_a \right), \quad (2)$$

where Σ_a is the macroscopic absorption cross section, D is the diffusion coefficient, and v is the neutron speed, respectively. From Eq. (1), the analytical solution of the Green's function can be expressed by:

$$n(x, t|x_0, t_0) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \varphi_n(x) \varphi_n(x_0) e^{-\alpha_n(t-t_0)}, \quad (3)$$

where α_n and $\varphi_n(x)$ represent the n th order α -eigenvalue and the corresponding eigenfunction ($n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$) that is self-adjoint. For example, in the case of a one-dimensional slab geometry, α_n and $\varphi_n(x)$ can be obtained as follows:

$$\alpha_n = v(\Sigma_a + DB_n^2), \quad (4)$$

$$\varphi_n(x) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{H}} \sin\left(B_n\left(x + \frac{H}{2}\right)\right), \quad (5)$$

$$B_n \equiv \frac{(n+1)\pi}{H}, \quad (6)$$

where B_n^2 represents the n th order geometric buckling, and H represents the slab thickness. In Eqs. (5) and (6), the zero-flux boundary condition is assumed as the boundary condition. In the case of an actual three-dimensional geometry, the analytical solution for the Green's function $n(\mathbf{r}, t | \mathbf{r}_0, t_0)$ can also be expressed as the sum of exponential functions in a similar way as Eq. (3), by modifying the analytical solutions of the geometric buckling, the α -eigenvalues, and the eigenfunctions [10].

2.2. Single Detection Probability

First, let us consider the probability of detecting a single neutron at the time t_1 . If $S(x)$ represents the spatial distribution of the ^{252}Cf source strength, $S(x_b)dx_b dt_b$ corresponds to the probability that a spontaneous fission event occurs within the time interval from t_b to $t_b + dt_b$ and the spatial range from x_b to $x_b + dx_b$. The probability that q neutrons are simultaneously emitted in this event is denoted as $D(q)$ [12]. Based on the Green's function of Eq. (3), $n(x_1, t_1 | x_b, t_b)dx_1$ represents the survival probability that a neutron emitted at the time t_b and the position x_b survives until the later time t_1 and the position x_1 . Then, the surviving neutron is detected with the probability of $\Sigma_d(x_1)v dt_1$ within the time interval from t_1 to $t_1 + dt_1$ and the spatial range of the position from x_1 to $x_1 + dx_1$. Here, $\Sigma_d(x)$ denotes the macroscopic detection cross section. By integrating and summing the above-mentioned probabilities over the entire range of x_b, x_1, t_b and q , the single detection probability $P_1(t_1)dt_1$, which is the probability that one neutron is detected during the time from t_1 to $t_1 + dt_1$, can be obtained as follows:

$$P_1(t_1)dt_1 = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{\mathcal{S}_n \mathcal{D}_n}{\alpha_n} dt_1, \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \because P_1(t_1)dt_1 &= \int_{-H/2}^{H/2} dx_b \int_{-H/2}^{H/2} dx_1 \int_{-\infty}^{t_1} dt_b S(x_b) \sum_{q=0}^{\infty} D(q)q \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \varphi_n(x_1)\varphi_n(x_b)e^{-\alpha_n(t_1-t_b)} v \Sigma_d(x_1) dt_1 \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\alpha_n} \left(\int_{-H/2}^{H/2} \langle q \rangle S(x_b) dx_b \right) \left(\int_{-H/2}^{H/2} \Sigma_d(x_1)\varphi_n(x_1) v dx_1 \right) dt_1, \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

$$\mathcal{S}_n \equiv \int_{-H/2}^{H/2} \langle q \rangle S(x)\varphi_n(x) dx, \quad (9)$$

$$\mathcal{D}_n \equiv \int_{-H/2}^{H/2} \Sigma_d(x)\varphi_n(x) v dx, \quad (10)$$

where, to simplify the derived theoretical equation, we define the coefficients \mathcal{S}_n and \mathcal{D}_n concerning the n th mode components of the neutron source and detection events.

2.3. Pair Detection Probability

Next, let us consider the probability of detecting two neutrons as a pair. As illustrated in Figure 1, two scenarios are conceivable for the detection of these two neutrons: a) the detection of neutrons originating from different spontaneous fissions; and b) the detection of neutrons originating from the same spontaneous fission.

Figure 1. Process of pair detection probability.

In case a), the neutron pair is detected with the single detection probability for each of the two neutron families. Therefore, by taking the product of two single detection probabilities, the detection probability of this uncorrelated scenario $P_{2,\text{uncor}}(t_1, t_2)dt_1dt_2$ can be expressed as follows:

$$P_{2,\text{uncor}}(t_1, t_2)dt_1dt_2 = P_1(t_1)P_1(t_2)dt_1dt_2 = \left(\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{\mathcal{S}_n \mathcal{D}_n}{\alpha_n} \right)^2 dt_1dt_2, \quad (11)$$

In case b), the correlated neutron pair is detected through the branching process of one neutron family. By considering one out of the q fission neutrons is detected within the time interval from t_1 to $t_1 + dt_1$, out of the remaining $(q - 1)$ neutrons is subsequently detected within the time interval from t_2 to $t_2 + dt_2$. Therefore, in a similar derivation process to Eq. (8), this detection probability $P_{2,\text{cor}}(t_1, t_2)dt_1dt_2$ can be obtained by

$$P_{2,\text{cor}}(t_1, t_2)dt_1dt_2 = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{\mathcal{S}_{mn} \mathcal{D}_m \mathcal{D}_n}{\alpha_m + \alpha_n} e^{-\alpha_n(t_2-t_1)} dt_1dt_2, \quad (12)$$

$$\mathcal{S}_{mn} \equiv \int_{-H/2}^{H/2} \langle q(q-1) \rangle S(x) \varphi_m(x) \varphi_n(x) dx, \quad (13)$$

where the coefficient \mathcal{S}_{mn} is introduced to represent the term related to the branching process of the source event due to the m th and n th mode components. Consequently, the total pair detection probability $P_2(t_1, t_2)dt_1dt_2$ can be obtained by the following summation of Eqs. (11) and (12):

$$P_2(t_1, t_2)dt_1dt_2 = \left(\left(\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{\mathcal{S}_n \mathcal{D}_n}{\alpha_n} \right)^2 + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{\mathcal{S}_{mn} \mathcal{D}_m \mathcal{D}_n}{\alpha_m + \alpha_n} e^{-\alpha_n(t_2-t_1)} \right) dt_1 dt_2, \quad (14)$$

2.4. Expected Values of Neutron Counts and Neutron Pairs

In the neutron noise measurement, neutrons are successively detected using a counting gate width T . Here, the number of detected neutrons within the counting gate width T is denoted as $C(T)$.

The expected value of detected neutron counts $\langle C(T) \rangle$ can be calculated by integrating $P_1(t_1)dt_1$ of Eq. (7) over the $0 \leq t_1 \leq T$:

$$\langle C(T) \rangle = \int_0^T P_1(t_1)dt_1 = C_R T, \quad (15)$$

$$C_R = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{\mathcal{S}_n \mathcal{D}_n}{\alpha_n}, \quad (16)$$

where, C_R corresponds to the average value of the neutron count rate in the steady state.

Similarly, the expected value of the neutron pairs detected during T , $\langle C(C-1)/2 \rangle$, can be calculated by the double integral of $P_2(t_1, t_2)dt_1dt_2$ shown in Eq. (14) over the range $0 \leq t_1 < t_2 \leq T$:

$$\frac{\langle C(T)(C(T)-1) \rangle}{2} = \int_0^T dt_2 \int_0^{t_2} dt_1 P_2(t_1, t_2) = \frac{1}{2} \langle C(T) \rangle^2 + T \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{\mathcal{S}_{mn} \mathcal{D}_m \mathcal{D}_n}{\alpha_n (\alpha_m + \alpha_n)} \left(1 - \frac{1 - e^{-\alpha_n T}}{\alpha_n T} \right), \quad (17)$$

2.5. Feynman- α method

In the Feynman- α method, the second-order neutron correlation factor $Y(T)$ is defined as follows:

$$Y(T) \equiv \frac{\langle C(T)(C(T)-1) \rangle - \langle C(T) \rangle^2}{\langle C(T) \rangle}, \quad (18)$$

where Y means the relative deviation of the variance $\langle C^2(T) \rangle - \langle C(T) \rangle^2$ from that of the Poisson distribution. Based on the theoretical derivation results using the heuristic method described above, the theoretical formula for $Y(T)$ can be finally obtained by substituting Eqs. (15) and (17) into Eq. (18):

$$Y(T) \equiv \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} Y_{n,\infty} \left(1 - \frac{1 - e^{-\alpha_n T}}{\alpha_n T} \right), \quad (19)$$

$$Y_{n,\infty} \equiv \frac{2}{C_R} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{\mathcal{S}_{mn} \mathcal{D}_m \mathcal{D}_n}{\alpha_n (\alpha_m + \alpha_n)} = \frac{1}{C_R} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{\mathcal{S}_{mn} \mathcal{D}_m \mathcal{D}_n}{\alpha_m \alpha_n}, \quad (20)$$

where $Y_{n,\infty}$ denotes the saturation value of the Y value for the n th mode component when $T \rightarrow \infty$. Similar to the theoretical formula for a neutron multiplication system [13], Eq. (19) clarifies the functional shape of $Y(T)$ can be expressed as a summation over all modes using the unique function of

the Feynman- α method, $\left(1 - \frac{1 - e^{-\alpha n T}}{\alpha n T}\right)$, even in a non-multiplication system with the multiple emission sources. Here, the fundamental mode of the eigenvalue α_0 corresponds to the most dominant neutron decay constant.

Equation (20) implies that the influence of the higher-order mode component can be reduced by setting a point neutron detector and/or a point neutron source at the nodes (the zero point) of the higher-order mode of the α -eigenfunction. For example, when the ^{252}Cf source with the strength S_0 is placed at the position $x = x_s$, the coefficient \mathcal{S}_{mn} can be expressed by

$$\mathcal{S}_{mn} = \langle q(q-1) \rangle S_0 \varphi_n(x_s) \varphi_m(x_s). \quad (21)$$

Therefore, by placing the ^{252}Cf source at a position $\varphi_n(x_s) = 0$, the corresponding n th mode component will not be excited in the measured $Y(T)$.

3. PRELIMINARY EXPERIMENT

3.1. Experimental Conditions

We conducted a neutron noise measurement in a non-multiplying system with a ^{252}Cf neutron source to analyze the α value using the Feynman- α method [9]. The preliminary experiment used polyethylene blocks to construct the experimental system. The size of the polyethylene rectangular cuboid was $400 \times 300 \times 150$ mm. To reduce the influence of the higher-order mode components as much as possible, the ^{252}Cf neutron source ($\sim 3.5 \times 10^5$ neutrons/s) was set at the center of a polyethylene rectangular cuboid, i.e., cylindrical cavity with a diameter of 10 mm, depth of 40 mm. Neutrons were detected using a BF_3 proportional counter (CENTRONIC) with a diameter of 25 mm and a length of 220 mm. The BF_3 detector was placed at the center of the upper plane of the rectangular cuboid, so that the cylindrical axis of BF_3 was parallel to the long side (400 mm). The detection signal from BF_3 was amplified by a preamplifier, followed by a shaping amplifier. The detection signal was saved as list-mode data using a digital MCA (ANSeeN, HSDMCA) to record the detection time and the pulsed height. After discriminating the pulse height to distinguish the neutron and the gamma signals, the time series data of the neutron noise was finally obtained. The total measurement time and the count rates C_R were ~ 40 hours and 512.50 ± 0.06 cps, respectively.

3.2. Experimental Results

Figure 2 shows the variation of Y with the counting gate width T by the bunching method for the measured time series data of the neutron noise. The error bar in Fig. 2 was calculated based on the statistical error (1σ) estimation of $Y(T)$ proposed in our previous study [13]. $Y(T)$ value gradually increases and saturates as T increases. Note that the $Y(T)$ value is negatively biased due to the dead time effect of the BF_3 detector. The shape of $Y(T)$ can be well expressed by the unique function of the Feynman- α method, i.e., $\left(1 - \frac{1 - e^{-\alpha n T}}{\alpha n T}\right)$. The α value was estimated using the non-linear least-squares with the theoretical formula derived under the fundamental mode approximation and considering the detector dead time [14]. The preliminary experimental result of α was $7685 \pm 251 \text{ s}^{-1}$, which agreed well with the α -eigenvalue calculation result ($\alpha = 7575 \text{ s}^{-1}$) using the deterministic transport calculation code GENESIS [15] within the fitting error.

Figure 2. Preliminary result of neutron noise.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study confirmed that an integral experiment for the neutron decay constant α can be simply conducted in a non-multiplying system using a ^{252}Cf multiple emission source. The derived theoretical formula clarifies that $Y(T)$ in a non-multiplying system can be expressed as a sum of the unique function of the Feynman- α method, $\left(1 - \frac{1-e^{-\alpha_n T}}{\alpha_n T}\right)$. Through the preliminary neutron noise measurement for the polyethylene blocks, we demonstrated that $Y(T)$ can be analyzed even for a non-multiplying system and the α value for the target system will be possible using the fitting method.

A future research topic is to design a measurement system to precisely measure the $Y(T)$ value. Another topic is to consider other neutron noise measurement techniques such as the Rossi- α method [16].

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